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COMMUNICATION (ENGLISH LANGUAGE)**

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Press freedom in Uzbekistan Uzbekistan

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Faculty: Master's degree

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6642949>

Annotation: This article deals with Uzbekistan's press freedom. In response, the media is rethinking how to study and compare languages for long-term approval.

Key words: press, media, ranking

World Press Freedom Index 2022: new era of polarization 20th edition of the RSF World Press Freedom Index indicates an aggravation of polarization, enhanced information chaos: polarization of the media leading to a split within countries, and polarization among states at the international level. The World Press Freedom Index, which evaluates the conditions in which journalistic activities are carried out in 180 countries as well as Uzbekistan, indicates catastrophic consequences in 2022 information chaos (globalized and digital space with weakened regulation, contributing to the spread of false information and propaganda).

Uzbekistan climbs in press freedom rankings, but situation remains 'difficult'. In the Reporters Without Borders Press Freedom Index 2022, Uzbekistan ranked 133rd. A year earlier, the country was 24 positions lower. The drastic change is due to the update of the rating methodology. The situation with media freedom in the country is still assessed as "difficult". The international non-governmental organization Reporters Without Borders (Reporters sans frontières, RSF) on May 3, World Press Freedom Day, published the World Press Freedom Index 2022.

Uzbekistan in the 20th ranking ranked 133rd out of 180 countries and territories. In last year's ranking, the country was 24 positions lower - in 157th place. This was due to a change in the ranking methodology, which defines freedom of the press as "an effective opportunity for journalists - both individuals and collectives - to select, produce and disseminate information in the public interest, regardless of political, economic, legal and social interference and without endangering their physical and mental safety." Working with a committee of seven experts from the world of science and the media, RSF has introduced five new metrics that capture "the complexity of press freedom":

political context, legal framework, economic context, socio-cultural context, and security (each metric is rated on a scale from 0 to 100 points). The study was conducted by interviewing hundreds of journalists, scientists and human rights activists using an updated questionnaire (123 questions) over the past year. For some territories where the situation has changed dramatically (Russia, Ukraine and Mali), updates were carried out from January to March 2022.

“Due to this change in methodology, comparing positions and scores between 2021 and 2022 should be treated with caution,” the ranking authors warn. Positions in the rankings have risen sharply in many countries, including Uzbekistan's neighbors. After the release of the rating, the press secretary of the President of Uzbekistan Sherzod Asadov congratulated the representatives of the media sphere on “significant success, which became one of the results of important steps taken under the leadership of the President of our country to ensure freedom of speech, the formation of mass media expressing public opinion as the “fourth authorities”. Komil Allamjonov, former press secretary of the head of state, now head of the board of trustees of the Public Fund for the Development and Support of National Mass Media, also noted the improvement in Uzbekistan's position in the ranking. “This means that if the press is less disturbed, we have a chance to achieve an even higher result than this. As the President said, there is no turning back! Only forward!” he wrote. Addressing journalists and bloggers, he added: “Freedom is only achieved through struggle. So do not give up, dear colleagues. If we do this, get scared and disappointed, then human dignity will never become a value in this country. Human rights, justice will be lost. The most effective rabies vaccine is the press. Let's not let some people close their jaws on our throats. Let's expand our legal knowledge. Let's not stop there for the sake of the future of our nation, our children. Let's become a real fourth estate. Everything is in our own hands.”

Has the rating of Uzbekistan improved?

Uzbekistan remained in the category of countries where the situation with media freedom is assessed as “difficult”. There are 42 such countries in total (in 2013 there were 38). A “good” situation is observed in only 8 countries (26), “satisfactory” in 40 (27), “problematic” in 62 (69) and “very difficult” in a record 28 (20).

A brief overview of the situation in Uzbekistan says that since 2016, when the country changed its president, “the conditions for the media have improved only slightly, and criticism of the government remains a difficult matter.” The authors note that the authorities “largely” control not only the media, but also “a number

of bloggers." The government "still hasn't implemented the reforms needed to repeal laws that allow pressure on the media. In a country where 60% of the population is under 30, social media groups are popular. They allow users to exchange information about corruption, which is practically not covered by the official media, the authors of the rating write. Journalists who spent many years in prison and were released were not rehabilitated. Bloggers receive threats, some are arrested, the review notes. An example is given of Otabek Sattoriy, who in May 2021 was sentenced to 6.5 years in prison on charges of libel and extortion. The organization notes that the blogger was framed. Having taken 133rd position in the ranking compared to 157th for the previous year, Uzbekistan received 45.74 points out of 100 possible, including 44.75 (129th place) in the political context, 50.88 in the legal framework (136th), economic context - 35.71 (123rd), socio-cultural context - 53.33 (138th) and security - 44.03 (129th). A year earlier, the country had 49.26 points, but here it is also worth considering the change in methodology. The closest neighbors of Uzbekistan in the rating were Uganda (132nd) and Algeria (134th). Kazakhstan is located on the 122nd line (+33 positions compared to the previous year), Tajikistan - on the 152nd (+10), Turkmenistan - on the 177th (+1). Kyrgyzstan ranked 72nd (+7), once again becoming the only country in Central Asia that has "relative freedom of expression and the press, despite an unstable economy and widespread official corruption."

"Catastrophic Consequences of Information Chaos"— RSF notes that the results of the ranking indicate "the catastrophic consequences in 2022 of information chaos - a globalized and digital space with a loose regulation that contributes to the spread of false information and propaganda."

The World Press Freedom Index, which evaluates the conditions in which journalistic activities are carried out in 180 countries and regions, indicates catastrophic consequences in 2022 information chaos (globalized and digital space with weakened regulation, contributing to the spread of false information and propaganda). The Development of Opinion Journalism on the Fox Model News in democratic societies and wide distribution of channels misinformation, reinforced by the work of social networks, cause an increase public controversy. At the international level, the asymmetry between open societies on the one hand, and despotic regimes that control their media and their information platforms by propaganda wars, on the other hand, weaken democratic regimes. On the both levels, this double polarization is an amplifying factor tension. In the 180 countries assessed by RSF, these indicators are measured at based on a

quantitative study of abuses against journalists and the media, as well as qualitative research based on answers to 123 questions from hundreds of selected RSF press freedom experts (Journalists, scientists and human rights activists). The questionnaire has been updated to it is better to take into account some issues, especially those related to digitalization of the media. In connection with this change in the methodology for comparing positions and numbers scores between 2021 and 2022 should be treated with caution. Collection data was discontinued at the end of January 2022, but from January to March 2022 years, updates were made for some territories where the situation changed dramatically (Russia, Ukraine and Mali).

References:

1. Thomas Hanitzsch, researcher at the Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich Faculty of Communication Studies and Media, specializing in particular in world journalistic cultures and comparative methodology;
2. David Levy, scientist Fellow and former director of the Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, member of the British RSF office;
3. Sally Hughes, professor of journalism and media management University of Miami, former journalist for the Miami Herald, Washington Post, and Maclean's;
4. Hermann Wasserman, professor of media studies at the University of Cape Town and editor of the journal African Journalism Studies;
5. Laura Moore, Journalist, Head of Research and Evaluation Deutsche Welle Akademie, author of Measuring Global Media Freedom (Springer VS, 2020); Thibault Bruttin, Deputy General Director of RSF;
6. Prem Sami when she was responsible for compiling the RSF World Press Freedom Index, and Nalini Lepeti-SHELLA, who came to replace her. With the support and assistance of the Director of Research Institut de recherche pour le développement
7. Jean-Daniel Zucker, director of Institute for Development Studies (Institut de recherche pour le development).